
Semantic Shifts of English Technological Terms in Uzbek Media

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Annotation *In recent years, rapid technological advancement has significantly increased global communication and widespread adoption of English technological terminology between different languages, including Uzbek. This article investigates the semantic shifts of English technological terms in Uzbek media discourse. The study examines several examples of active usage of English terms from online newspapers, social media sites, and technology news portals. It is indicated that when technological terms are adopted into Uzbek media language, they often go through semantic changes such as broadening, narrowing and metaphorical extension. In many cases, borrowed words adjust to the Uzbek language's lexicon and get new conceptual meanings. In other words, currently, Uzbek media – including television programs, blogs, news websites and social media – frequently use English-derived terms such as "platform", "blog", "trend", "content", "channel" which have acquired extra semantic complexities in Uzbek media usage. The study emphasizes how the media shapes new semantic interpretations of borrowed terminology and disseminates technology language. The findings provide explanations with knowledge of lexical borrowing and semantic transformation in today's Uzbek language use.*

Keywords *Semantic shift, English technological terms, Uzbek media, borrowed terms, technological terminology, media discourse*

O'zbek ommaviy axborot vositalarida ishlatiladigan ingliz tilidan o'zlashtirilgan texnologiyaga oid atamalarning semantik o'zgarishi

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Annotatsiya *So'nggi yillardagi texnologiyaning jadal rivojlanishi global aloqaning va turli tillar, jumladan o'zbek tili o'rtasida inglizcha texnologik terminlarning keng qo'llanilishini sezilarli darajada oshishiga sabab bo'ldi. Ushbu maqola o'zbek media diskursidagi inglizcha texnologik atamalarning semantik siljishini o'rganadi. Tadqiqot onlayn gazetalar, ijtimoiy tarmoqdagi saytlar va texnologiyaga oid yangiliklar portallaridagi inglizcha atamalarning faol ishlatilishiga oid bir qancha misollarni tahlil qiladi. Ta'kidlanishicha, texnologik atamalar o'zbek ommaviy axboroti tiliga o'zlashtirilganida, odatda ular ma'no kengayishi, torayishi va majoziy kengayish kabi semantik o'zgarishlarga uchraydi. Ko'p holatlarda, o'zlashtirilgan so'zlar o'zbek tili leksikasiga moslashadi va yangi nazariy ma'noga ega bo'ladi. Boshqacha qilib*

aytganda, hozirgi kunga kelib o'zbek mediasi – teledasturlar, bloglar, yangiliklar veb-saytlari va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda ingliz tilidan kelib chiqqan atamalar, jumladan, "platforma", "blog", "trend", "kontent", "kanal" kabi atamalar tez-tez ishlatilib, o'zbek mediasida semantik murakkabliklarga ega bo'lmoqda. Tadqiqot o'zlashtirilgan terminologiyaning yangi semantik talqinlarini qanday qilib shakllantirishiga va texnologiya tilini tarqalishiga urg'u beradi. Izlanish natijalari hozirgi kundagi o'zbek tili leksik o'zlashuvi va semantik o'zgarishiga borasidagi tushuntirishlarni olib boradi.

Kalit so'zlar *Semantik siljish, inglizcga texnologik atamalar, o'zbek media, o'zlashgan so'zlar, texnologik terminologiya, media diskursi*

Семантические изменения английских технологических терминов в узбекских СМИ

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Аннотация *В последние годы стремительное технологическое развитие значительно расширило глобальную коммуникацию и широкое распространение английской технологической терминологии между различными языками, включая узбекский. В данной статье исследуются семантические изменения английских технологических терминов в дискурсе узбекских СМИ. В исследовании рассматриваются несколько примеров активного использования английских терминов в онлайн-газетах, социальных сетях и новостных порталах о технологиях. Показано, что при заимствовании технологических терминов в язык узбекских СМИ они часто претерпевают семантические изменения, такие как расширение, сужение и метафорическое расширение. Во многих случаях заимствованные слова адаптируются к лексикону узбекского языка и приобретают новые концептуальные значения. Другими словами, в настоящее время узбекские СМИ – включая телепрограммы, блоги, новостные сайты и социальные сети – часто используют термины, заимствованные из английского языка, такие как «платформа», «блог», «тренд», «контент», «канал», которые приобрели дополнительную семантическую сложность в использовании в узбекских СМИ. В исследовании подчеркивается, как средства массовой информации формируют новые семантические интерпретации заимствованной терминологии и распространяют язык технологий. Полученные результаты дают объяснения, основанные на знании лексического заимствования и семантической трансформации в современном использовании узбекского языка.*

Ключевые слова *Семантический сдвиг, английские технологические термины, узбекские СМИ, заимствованные термины, технологическая терминология, медиадискурс*

Introduction

The ongoing development of digital technologies and the growth of worldwide communication have had a profound influence on the lexical development of many languages. As a result of them, English has become the dominant lingua franca and the main source of shaping the technological terminology used in modern media discourse around the globe (Crystal, 2003). As new technological developments emerge, many English technology related words have entered the Uzbek language, especially through mass media, online platforms and social networking sites.

Since online journalism, digital communication and social media have advanced in Uzbekistan, English technological terms have adapted to everyday language. In order to describe contemporary digital phenomena, such as online platforms, digital content, social networks and communication, Uzbek media uses borrowed terminology regularly. However, when these words are borrowed and integrated into Uzbek, these meanings do not always stay the same as in English (Traugott & Dasher, 2002).

Semantic shift is regarded as the process when a word acquires a new connotation, it loses its denotative meaning, partially or entirely (Ullmann, 1957). Semantic shift is important for better understanding how language has evolved throughout the period and how it has impacted on adaptation of communication. While borrowing the technological terms into a language, they are broadened, narrowed, or metaphorically reinterpreted depending on how they are used in the received language.

Despite the fact that several studies have already analyzed borrowing words in Uzbek and other languages, semantic shifts of English technological terms in Uzbek media have not been explored yet. In order to identify crucial patterns of their adaptation within Uzbek media discourse, this article will discuss how English technological terms experience semantic shifts in Uzbek media.

Literature review

The evolution of word meanings over time due to cultural, social, and technological changes is known as semantic shift, or semantic change. Semantic shifts can be divided into broadening, narrowing, amelioration, pejoration, and metaphorical or metonymical shifts (Ullmann, 1962). Semantic shifts frequently result from changes in communicative needs, cultural transitions, and the creation of new social realities (Traugott and Dasher, 2002). Because of the development of societies and the existence of new technologies, new words are added and languages change over time.

Furthermore, one of the most important ways that new vocabulary enters a language is through borrowing. According to Haugen (1950), borrowing is the process of incorporating linguistic components from one language into another. As borrowed words adjust to the linguistic and cultural context of the recipient language, they may subsequently experience alterations in meanings. This theory proves that English borrowed technological terms can also be adapted to the Uzbek language.

Linguistic studies have also highlighted how media discourse plays a role in the dissemination of borrowed terms. Mass media, especially in the context of digital

communication, can effectively introduce new terminology into ordinary English (Fairclough, 1995). New words spread fast to a large audience through news portals, social networking sites and internet journalism before progressively becoming part of everyday speech.

The impact of foreign borrowings on the evolution of contemporary Uzbek vocabulary has drawn more attention from academics studying the Uzbek language. It is inevitable that English loanwords are particularly common in the domains of media communication, marketing and technology. As these acquired phrases are incorporated into Uzbek language, they frequently experience semantic change.

The semantic shift of English technological terms in Uzbek media discourse is still largely unexplored although several studies have examined the broad process of lexical borrowing in Uzbek. Examining how technology concepts alter meaning in media contexts is crucial for comprehending the continuous development of the Uzbek lexicon, given the increasing impact of digital media and social networks in Uzbekistan. Therefore, by examining the semantics changes of English technological phrases used in Uzbek media, this article explains how to advance current linguistic research.

Methodology

This article outlines the research methodology to analyze semantic shifts of English technological terms in Uzbek media.

Literature review

This method is carried out to understand the theoretical and linguistic perspectives in existing scholarly works about semantic change, lexical borrowing, and media language. It is also based on helping find out the most important key concepts and the differences.

Semantic mapping and Conceptual analysis

Semantic mapping is used to investigate how Uzbek usage of English technological

terms alters their meanings. Using this strategy helps find relationships between original meanings and recently learned meanings in various settings. The interpretation of these meanings within the Uzbek linguistic and cultural context is supported by conceptual analysis.

Sociolinguistic approach

The sociolinguistic approach is used to examine how language use is impacted by social factors, including media influence, digital communication, and globalization. This approach aids in explaining the widespread adoption of English technological terms and how they are used in Uzbek society's daily communication.

Media discourse analysis

The usage of English technological words in Uzbek media texts, such as blogs, social media platforms, and online news is examined through media discourse analysis. This approach focuses on how borrowed terminology is disseminated, modified, and reinterpreted through media channels (Fairclough, 1995). Furthermore, it aids in determining usage patterns and contextual meanings in everyday communication.

Analysis and Discussion

This study examines semantic shifts of specific English technological terms in Uzbek media discourse adopting the methods mentioned above. By analyzing these terms in Uzbek media significant semantic changes, such as broadening, narrowing and metaphorical extension are revealed.

According to Cambridge dictionary, the term "platform" means a form of social networking and computer programs that enables people to interact, send their videos, photos and exchange information on the internet. However, the definition of platform has broadened to encompass a variety of online places, including social media pages, Telegram channels and online discussion forums. Consequently, repeated exposure to online news stories and social media messages have normalized the term's generalized

meaning and have resulted in semantic broadening.

However, the term "blog" can be an example for semantic narrowing. In Cambridge dictionary, it refers to any websites that people share information and their daily lives on a daily basis, while in Uzbek media, it is most frequently used to refer to private content posted on social media sites, especially Instagram and Telegram. The term's functional specialization within local digital practices, where online content production is dominated by influencer activity and personal impression, is reflected in this narrowing.

Metaphorical extension can also be seen in terms including trend and content. In Uzbek media, the term "trend" refers to viral themes, popular online conversations, or trendy digital occurrences, but in English, it typically refers to a broad direction or tendency. The term "content" includes creative articles, marketing materials, influencer-generated media, and informational content. These changes demonstrate how cultural and communicative settings affect how borrowed language is adapted, which is consistent with research showing that changing social realities and technology advancements frequently lead to semantic change (Traugott and Dasher, 2002; Ullman, 1962).

The way that continuous usage normalize new meanings is one way that media discourse has an impact. The link between language and communication practices is demonstrated by media channels, which are crucial in spreading and reinforcing linguistic patterns (Fairclough, 1995). Social media sites and online news portals help this process even more in the context of Uzbek media. These findings show that technological concepts are actively

reinterpreted and assimilated into Uzbek, taking on culturally and contextually particular meanings.

Overall, the analysis demonstrates that both local adaptation processes and global impacts are reflected in semantic modifications in Uzbek media. Uzbek speakers adapt borrowed English terminology to suit communicative and conceptual demands, media outlets play a crucial role in creating and disseminating these changing meanings.

Conclusion

This article examines the semantic changes of some technological terms in Uzbek media discourse. According to the investigation, borrowed English technological terms, such as blog, trend, and content undergo semantic changes including broadening, narrowing and metaphorical expansion. More specifically, the meaning of the term "platform" has broadened to encompass a variety of online sites, while the meaning of the term "blog" has narrowed in its relationship with personal social media content. Metaphorical extension is also seen in the examples, like "trend" and "content", which represent their adaptation to digital communication methods.

The results show how the importance of media discourse in forming and normalizing these new meanings. Borrowed terminology are incorporated into Uzbek with different cultural meanings on account of their frequent use in social media and online news. To summarize, the study demonstrates the ongoing development of Uzbek lexicon in the digital era by confirming that both local communicative demands and global technological influence cause semantic shifts.

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